

Globalization, Greed and Glocal Ecology: A Psychological Perspective

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Abstract

Evidently, a globalized society causes global environmental crises. Undoubtedly, survival of human life on the planet Earth is threatened. Is there any connection between globalization, environmental crises and psychological manifestations? What are the psychological perspectives linking the ecological damages from local to the global scale? This article explores such intricate relationships and discusses the implications. The underlying principal cause is human's unending greed to acquire maximum materials and power to control the planet and entire humanity. The greed is believed to be a bottomless pit which exhausts the person in an endless effort to satisfy the need without ever reaching satisfaction. The greedy people are supposed to have biological, psychological and sociological drives. Evidently, global destruction of the ecosystems and natural environment are directly or indirectly linked to unprecedented chronic human greed and self-indulgence. Undoubtedly, unencumbered chronic greed of a few elite institutions led by top capitalists has put the entire planet in havoc and infiltrated widespread sufferings at the global scale. Conclusively, psychological basis of environmental problems has a sociological and socio-historical scope within the frame of globalization. Psychological account of the environmental crisis is explained subsequently in this article followed by a case study of deforestation of Carpathian Mountains staged by a greedy Austrian man.

Keywords

Greedy; Globalization; Ecological impact; Psychological perspective; Environmental destruction

Introduction: The Globalization

In the modern world, the telecommunications and global economic freedom have changed the landscape of people's movements across the borders and world regions (Arnett, 2002). In the book "The Battle in Seattle, 1999", The Economist magazine writes that exports manifested in world gross domestic product (WGDP) grew from 8% in 1950 to 26% by 1998, and global travels increased by 700% since 1960 (Held, 1998). Began in 19902, globalization is known to be a complex process having varying pace and direction ascertained by different factors such as economic, social, and environmental determinants. The environmental definition of the globalization reveals that the globalization should be considered as a process of resulting environmental crises caused by global environmental externalities (e.g., pollution) (Ilić and Hafner, 2015). Hence, a globalized society causes global environmental crises. As a result, survival of human life on the planet Earth is threatened (Ilić and Hafner, 2015). Is there any connection between globalization, environmental crises and psychological manifestations? What are the psychological perspectives linking the ecological damages from local to the global scale? This article will explore such intricate relationships and discuss the implications. Arnett (2002) articulates that psychology explores indirectly the globalization in terms of psychological theory, research on acculturation, identity, and other implications.

Greed

Amid the complexity of the human behaviour, the psychology explores greed as causative agent for environmental destruction by economic externalities. Robertson (2013) defines the greed as one psychological phenomenon characterized with the selfish quest to possess objects, people, wealth, substances, status, appreciation, power, or attention beyond the extent required for basic human comfort. To simply put, Webster (2013) defined the greed as an excessive desire for more. It manifests a state of insatiability exhibiting quest for obtaining preferred goods. Scientists have further described the greed beyond mere accumulation and opined that greed may be characterized by causing potentially negative consequences that emanate from one's own actions. Apparently, an excessive desire for something is usually at the expense of others (Mussel and Hewig, 2013). Certain scientists attributed trait greed shares with other dark traits like psychopathy and machiavellianism (Furnham *et al.*, 2013; Moshagen *et al.*, 2018). Another scholar, D'Souza (1995), classified the greed as the direct outcome of dissatisfaction, emptiness, and discontentment. He argued further that an act of filling emptiness and discontentment, the greedy individual acts to acquire more resources, admiration and power, often at the cost of the comfort, livelihood and happiness of other individuals (D'Souza, 1995). As a result, greed comprises an ability to cause profound human suffering. Fromm (1939) quoted famously, "Greed is a bottomless pit which exhausts the person in an endless effort to satisfy the need without ever reaching satisfaction". According to D'Souza (1995), greed has a potential to cause sufferings at (local) community level as well as global (wider) level. At the global level, possible outcomes of greed and self-indulgence are manifested in the form of wars, extreme poverty, social instability, invasions, massacres, over-population, economic crises and climate change (D'Souza, 1995).

It is interesting to understand the epistemology of greed and acquisitiveness. The greedy people are supposed to have biological, psychological and sociological drives (D'Souza, 1995). The American Psychiatric Association (APA) articulated that greed is closely associated with biological and psychological disorders such as Narcissistic Personality Disorder (NPD), substance addiction, behavioral addiction, Obsessive-Compulsive Personality Disorder (OCPD) and Anti-Social Personality Disorder (ASPD) (Angres and Bettinardi-Angres, 2008; American Psychiatric Association, 2000). Can we relate these disorders with the state of addiction? The research on addiction suggests that disturbed balance of neurotransmitters and hormones (e.g., dopamine) can be attributed to substance addictions (Salamone, 1992; Crews, Zou and Qin, 2011; Kauer and Malenka, 2007). Psychiatrists established that behavioral or soft addictions have neurobiological correlation to dopamine (Di Chiara and Bassareo, 2007; Girault and Greengard, 2004; Brewer and Potenza, 2008). Camarena *et al.* (2001) and Denys, Zohar and Westenberg (2004) have created

an evidence linking Obsessive-Compulsive Personality Disorder (OCPD), dopamine and serotonin hormonal regulation. Anti-Social Personality Disorder (ASPD) is found being caused by high testosterone and low serotonin levels in human body (Black, 2007; Sjöberg *et al.*, 2007). Famous psychologists, Freud and Maslow, recognized greed as a mental disorder and they strongly correlated the greed with narcissism and meta-pathology (Schultz and Schultz, 2004; Freud, 1914). Narcissistic Personality Disorder (NPD) is also believed to be primarily a psychological problem originated in an individual generally through negative childhood attachment styles (Groopman and Cooper, 1995), though inheritance and sociological factors also contribute to its development (Schulze *et al.*, 2013). Usually, majority of individuals suffering from NPD does not seek any solution as they do not treat this problem as an illness (Golomb, 1995). To understand the concept of greed and acquisitive behavior, psychoanalyses reckon that there is a strong correlation between early negative attachment styles and acquisitive behavior (Nikelly, 2006).

Beyond medico-psychiatric analysis, phenomenon of globalization can be linked with the greed through the capitalism, which is master driver for self-interests and the quest for profits. The force of capitalism demands the use of advertising bombardment for goods and services, and massive advertising leads to high competition, envy and acquisitiveness (Lasch, 1991; Holbrook, 1987). Paradoxically, in a capitalistic society, narcissism and self-interests are admired rather than rejected. Nikelly (2006) argues that vast economic and social inequalities in a society lead to severe problems of mental and physical health that develop gradually into mental disorders and addictions.

Environment

A “common heritage of mankind” is the tag used for the environment. The environmental issues are increasingly the cross-boundary and global issues, since it is impossible for one national alone to tackle these problems (Basler, 2011). The globalization is a process considered manifesting local and global environmental crises at massive scale; therefore, the problems emanating from the global economic crisis are now beyond the scope of national and regional frameworks. They are evidently global. Expanded especially after 1991, globalization brought in growth of international trade and financial surges, coupled with extended cooperation among countries and innovations in the sphere of science and technology. However, it has brought in enormous environmental destruction wherever it has occurred (D’Souza, 1995). Ilić and Hafner (2015) identified main causes of environmental problems to be the industrial production, development of traffic, growth of energy production, development of technics and technology, unprecedented exploitation of natural resources, and chemical contamination of soil and foods. Today, civilizational development has inevitably caused the gradual emergence of global warming and climate change on the planet (Ilić and Hafner, 2015).

In November 2013, the World Economic Forum commissioned a Global Risks Perception Survey (GRPS) involving 1,000 experts of economics, society, geopolitics, environment, and technology (Schwab, 2014). This GRPS identified 3 out of 10 top risks pertaining to environment: water crises, failure of climate change mitigation and adaptation, and extreme weather events. So, explicitly, the environment occupies one-third space among all the consequences that come up from globalization process. An overwhelming scientific literature clearly spells out that the climate change occurs primarily due to surge of greenhouse gases produced as a result of anthropogenic activities (Change, 1996). It is known from many decades that greenhouse gases are emitted from industries, transport vehicles, combustion engines, and deforestation. But the world has failed mitigating climate change (Olivier, Peters and Janssens-Maenhout, 2012). More of this mitigation failure is attributed to free market capitalism carried over by excessive consumerism and corporate profits (Newell and Paterson, 2010; Klein, 2011). Precise example of greenhouse gases and resulting climate change is of developed road traffic. In other words, globalization, as a planetary process (Siriner *et al.*, 2011), has catalyzed the development of traffic. The transport infrastructure has, in turn, created a series of environmental problems, e.g., increased air pollution, high noise levels, taking up space, and unabated release of harmful and hazardous substances. In particular, traffic vehicles are mostly dependent on oil, which builds 14% of emissions into the atmosphere containing harmful gases that affect

human health (Radić Jovanović *et al.*, 2012). Thus, application of modern technology greatly contributes to global warming and increased emission of harmful gases. The global warming is a problem of ecological nature and disturbs vital functions of the planet Earth. Cited examples are the chief drivers of the resource use and exploitation, which directly spoil environmental quality and create significant environmental problems. The resource depletion beyond a threshold diminishes its ability to regenerate, brings thereby threatening with disappearance of resources (Ilić and Hafner, 2015).

For our daily life, globalization is perceived having far-reaching consequences. Is it boon or bane having faster access to technologies, effective communication networks, and bountiful innovations? There is a simple equation: development of technics and technology leads to industry evolution, development and proliferation, which adversely affects the environment. A stark example of technological advancement affecting the environment is the green revolution in agriculture. In a bid to accomplish higher agricultural production and protect the plants against pests and diseases, toxic chemicals are dosed into cropfields causing the contamination of whole agroecosystem. Notably, the use of chemicals to destroy weeds and other unwanted plants disturbs the balance in the agroecosystem. The food products obtained after the application of toxic chemicals in agriculture are proved to be very harmful to human health (Ilić and Hafner, 2015). As discussed above, the climate change is caused by anonymous human activities. To understand better the climate change, discussing weather variations seems important. Of late, weather's extreme events are observed more frequently. Heat waves, cold waves, and significant unseasonal and unusual tropical cyclones cause immense damages. The direct effects of extreme weather events can include famines, landslides, floods, draughts, and large-scale destruction of property and the ecosystem. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), economic cost of extreme weather events has risen since 1980 (Meehl *et al.*, 2000). IPCC and countless scientists have attributed extreme weather to human-induced temperature rise and greenhouse effects (Hansen *et al.*, 2000).

Nothing has caused faster apparent impact than the water scarcity, which is supposed primarily caused by over-utilization of water, climate change, increased pollution (Postel, 1997). This is a global problem now and can be attributed to either physical water scarcity or economic water scarcity. Economic water scarcity is connected to human greed and tendency to grab the resources. It is triggered by poor water management, corrupt governments, lack of property rights, bureaucratic inertia, overconsumption, and shortage of infrastructure investment (United Nations, 2006; Zetland, 2011). The water scarcity ultimately leads to the food insecurity. As the economists articulate, food insecurity is a product of the land degradation, global water crises, land grabbing, agricultural diseases, climate change, political corruption, and infringement of food sovereignty. Explicitly, almost all of the causes are directly attributed to corporate control and political powers that take over lands for the sake of profits. Among all these causes, land grabbing typically can be traced within countries and transboundary. Internationally, wealthy countries and powers purchase and acquire land in poorer countries in the name of corporate agriculture or industrialization. Blas and England (2008) informed that several middle eastern and western powers were involved in grabbing land in backward African countries. Similarly, political corruption in Sub-Saharan Africa has caused massive famines (Cunney and Hill, 1999). When we look behind, it is observed that the negative impacts of globalization on the environment overtake the positive ones. As explained in preceding para, the environmental destruction is not confined to national boundaries, rather it is transboundary and export oriented. Economic demand in one rich country induces the export of natural resources from poor or developing countries. For example, massive deforestation is going on in Ukrainian and Romanian Carpathians to export the wood to EU countries. Likewise, in Australia, about 90% of native forest trees is exported, thus destroying the natural heritage of Australia.¹ Moreover, according to WWF, the process of civilization and globalization has engulfed one-half of the forests once covered the Earth (Ilić and Hafner, 2015).

A discussion on how global environmental governance addresses the transboundary environmental damages is necessary. There must be an international body to address global problems and risks related to the

¹ <https://www.bushheritage.org.au/who-we-are/our-challenge/land-clearing>

environment, national conflicts, the global economy, geopolitics, and global political issues. Despite a number of global institutions i.e., World Bank, United Nations, International Monetary Fund, International Criminal Court, World Wildlife Fund, World Trade Organization, G-8, and North Atlantic Treaty Organization, exist, the greed-caused global environmental problems are not addressed adequately. Barnett and Duvall (2005) described this as the main reason behind failure of global governance to be attributed to power struggles between the developed countries being controlled by the global financial sector. Evidently, global destruction of the ecosystems and natural environment are directly or indirectly linked to unprecedented chronic human greed and self-indulgence. Undoubtedly, unencumbered chronic greed of a few elite institutions led by top capitalists has put the entire planet in havoc and infiltrated widespread sufferings at the global scale. In the same fashion, the greed is manifested at the community level too, as it causes same destruction at the local level (D'Souza 1995).

Conclusively, psychological basis of environmental problems has a sociological and socio-historical scope within the frame of globalization. With this backdrop, it is noted that globalization occurs in all areas of life, primarily in the economic, political, cultural, and psychological spheres (Smrečnik, 2002). Nevertheless, the environmental crisis refers to the global “invasion” on ecosystems, that is, the man’s immoral behavior towards nature (Malešević, 2004). Psychological account of the environmental crisis is explained subsequently.

Psychology of Environmental Destruction

An interplay of varied human behaviours cumulatively acting as drivers is responsible for the degradation of ecological components in the nature. It is the complex attitude of man to nature that has caused the destruction of forest resources, exploitation of ores and minerals, and extinction of countless species of flora and fauna. The energy consumption for industrial purposes has multiplied in less than a decade. Scholars predict that non-renewable energy sources, such as oil, will completely disappear by the end of the 21st century (Malešević, 2004). Truly articulated that man is the only creature on Earth who is destroying own survival through consumptive and destructive attitude towards nature. In Davies’ opinion, economics is the discipline that describes the way in which humans interact with the nature while ensuring the production and reproduction, which means that there is no environmental issue independent of economic relations (Davies, 2006). Since the advent of industrial society, it emphasized on maximum exploitation of nature and the environment, in order to extract maximum profits, while morality is usually ignored. With such exploitative attitudes of greedy humans, the significant destruction of nature occurs. Considering this background, Lomborg (2009) advocates for a radical change in the values and systems. Some call that Earth can be saved by promoting and imposing a spiritual dimension of environmental culture, which includes knowledge and habits, acceptance of norms about natural and social environment, adopted values, attitudes and beliefs, health care norms, and norms for quality of life (Koković, 2010).

According to Steg and Vlek (2009), “environmental behavior is driven by any or combination of three key factors: motivational factors (i.e., perceived costs and benefits, moral, and normative concerns and affect), contextual factors, and habitual behavior”. More elaborate views are given by Stern (2000) who identified “four causal variables for a given environmental behavior: attitudinal factors; contextual forces; personal capabilities; and habit or routine behaviors”. Steve Taylor, in his book *Back to Sanity*², suggests that human beings may be collectively suffering from a psychological disorder (‘humania’), and their reckless abuse of the environment is one of the foremost evidences (Taylor, 2014). He quoted the example of the Indigenous people how they have been consistently appalled by American white people’s lack of respect for the natural world, and a systematic abuse of nature by them. Taylor (2014) further quotes Chief Seattle comparing the white man, over 150 years ago, to “a stranger who comes in the night and takes from the land whatever he needs”. Having a great foresight, Chief Seattle warned then US President Franklin Pearce that his people

² http://www.amazon.com/Back-To-Sanity-Healing-Madness/dp/1848505477/ref=pd_sim_b_1?ie=UTF8&refRID=0JK02F53603SMK1JT7GK

"will devour the Earth and leave behind only a desert" (Taylor, 2014). Taylor (2014) has described psychological causes of human's abusive and exploitative attitude to nature. He explained two main psychological factors. The first, "over-developed sense of ego" is the intensified sense of individuality. He explained it by differentiating between western so-called "civilised" peoples and the nature-loving tribal Indigenous peoples. The Indigenous cultures have polytheistic diversity liked world visions. Usually, the Indigenous peoples do not exist as self-centric person, selfish being and egoist individuals. They reflect a collective and community identity embedded with their land. Taylor (2014) quotes the anthropologist Silberbauer who explained features of G/wi people of the Kalahari Desert of Africa. G/wi people bears an identity grossly 'group-referenced' rather than individual; resultantly, these Indigenous individuals identify themselves representing their kin or community group instead of their solitary identity (Silberbauer, 1994). Similarly, Boydell (2001) elaborated the Indigenous peoples of Fiji having a concept of "self-embedded-in-community [which] contrasts with the western value of individualism with its idea of the self as separate and separating from others". Such collective values underlie Indigenous peoples' strong belongingness to their land. They attribute their life to the land. The Fijian anthropologist Ravuva (1983) exclaimed that Fijian's attachment to their *vanua* or land is "an extension of the concept of self. To most Fijians the idea of parting with one's *vanua* or land is tantamount to parting with one's life". On the contrary, modern societies are full of heightened sense of individuality that sows duality and separation inherently. It cages our souls within our own egos. In the words of Taylor (2014), "we perceive nature as something other that we see natural phenomena as objects which we are entitled to use for our own devices".

Next is the 'de-sacralised' vision of nature is the modern man's inability to sense the natural processes. Our vision in the childhood has intense vividness and a liveliness, but our adulthood changes the perceptions of the world to become de-sensitised and automatic. It means the world transforms to a shadowy, one-dimensional place full of material and source of materialism. In the eyes of Aboriginal people, we the modern society lose the ability to dream natural being around us. It ultimately pushes us to treat natural phenomena as objects. Implications of this vision transformation from childhood to adulthood leads humans not to have any qualms about abusing and exploiting the natural world, tearing up its surface in search of resources and polluting it with our waste (Taylor, 2014). Thus, this psychological interpretation tends to change our dilemma even more dismal. To suggest a solution to this psychological problem, Taylor (2014) adds that "only sure way of ensuring our survival as a species would be for us to undergo a psychological shift – specifically, to transcend our sense of separateness and regain a sense of connection to nature and a "sacralised" vision of the natural world".

Case Study of Forest Destruction in Romanian and Ukrainian Carpathians

Not only in Carpathian Mountains, but in entire eastern Europe, the primary forests were existing in large areas. Some of the areas still have these primary forests. However, deforestation in Carpathian areas is rampant under the nose of the EU and domestic law enforcement agencies.

Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser (2020) exposes, "*Quantum of destruction of is horrific: 40 tree trunks every minute, 2400 every hour, 28,800 every shift. Virgin forests in Central-Eastern Europe are the last remaining ones on the continent, yet they are being mercilessly torn down. Part of this multi-billion Euro industry is a mafia-like system; Austrian timber companies are right at the heart of it*". According to Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser (2020), insatiable hunger for wood of an Austrian man, Gerald Schweighofer, has caused massive destruction in Carpathian Mountains of Ukraine and Romania. An environmental journalism group, Addendum³, investigated and exposed the forest destruction performed by Austrian company, Schweighofer, in Carpathian areas. Many governments including Romania and Poland have strictly monitored the activities of this Austrian company because of serious suspicion of involvement in the illegal logging of the last remaining primary forests in Eastern Europe. After the Addendum ran a campaign against

³ <https://www.addendum.org/>

Schweighofer, it has been removed from prestigious Forest Stewardship Council⁴ (FSC) certification of sustainably produced timber. An FSC investigation report claimed a “clear and convincing evidence” that Schweighofer was “involved systematically [...] directly and indirectly, in the trade of timber which has been harvested and/or handled in violation of existing laws and regulations” (Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser, 2020). Today, Gerald Schweighofer has a palace like home in central Vienna, and after 2002 he sold his sawmills in Austria to build vastly bigger structures in Romania. The Romanian politicians welcomed him, and he now has more than 3000 staff, a turnover of 762 million Euros and 5 factories in the country, producing pellets and sawn, glued and profiled timber supplied throughout the world (Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser, 2020). With annual turnover of more than 2 billion Euros, Kronospan is another company, which is world’s biggest manufacturer of wood-based panels supplying to Ikea. Operating jointly with Swiss Krono, the Kaindls⁵ is one of the main players in the Carpathians. Perhaps the Egger is largest global concern having 18 sites in 8 different countries.

The Global Forest Watch⁶ has estimated that 317,000 hectares of Romanian forest were lost to logging between 2001 and 2017. Since 2003, nearly 260 million Romanian trees have cleared. About 38.6 million cubic metres of timber was taken from Carpathian forests between 2014 and 2018 (Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser, 2020). It is articulated that half of these trees were in national parks or conservation areas. The forest utilisation plans of Romania permitted just 18 million cubic metres of wood, which means total amount felled was twice the legal limit. Remaining 20 million cubic metres of timber was actually extracted by mafia timber (Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser, 2020).

Describing the process of stealing the timber right at the site of operation, Mihail Hanzu, a qualified forestry engineer who used to be Forestry Inspector for a municipality near Sibiu, told to Addendum, “It was a whole system, from the mayor to my colleagues in the forestry department. I found more than 50 ways they were going about their fraud. The most common one was by deliberately understating the volumes. They mark a tree for felling. Write in the documents that it measures 18 metres, even if it actually measures 40, and that it has a diameter of 25 centimetres, even if it is actually 50. There is a great deal of money in that difference, and that money flows into their system. The municipality issues a licence for the logging, the companies sell the timber to middlemen, who store it in their timber yards and later deliver it to the sawmills along with all the necessary legal declarations” (Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser, 2020). In the words of David Gehl from the Environmental Investigation Agency (EIA), a US NGO investigating the predatory exploitation of nature throughout the world, “While the deforestation of the Amazon rainforest has been horrifying people for years, hardly anyone realises that Europe contains remnants of virgin forests that are just as important. The fact that the majority of these are on our doorstep, in the Carpathians, and are under threat remains an untold story.” The EIA reports spot Schweighofer for having been the “biggest receiver of illegal timber” and having “lied about the source of its products for more than 10 years”. Schweighofer receives timber from various sources, including Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Ukraine. Johannes Zahnen, a forestry expert with the WWF, pointed out that 2013 EU Timber Regulation⁷ has failed addressing cross-boundary deforestation, though it was supposed to stop the illegal timber trade in the EU region (Lehermayr, Reinhart and Kaiser, 2020).

Ukraine is an important timber supplier country. The Ukrainian railway reaches directly to the doors of the Schweighofer and Egger factories in Rădăuți, north of Romania. An environmental organisation Earthsight⁸ discovered in 2018 that Schweighofer alone was receiving 80 railway wagons every day from Ukraine. In Hungary, Kaindl family has opened a new chipboard factory right on border with Ukraine. In the Ukrainian Carpathians, one can witness bald forestlands. “In order to keep the timber well below the market price, foreign companies were willing to make payments to letter-box companies

⁴ <https://fsc.org/en/about-us>

⁵ <https://www.addendum.org/holzmafia/kaindl-kronospan/>

⁶ <https://www.globalforestwatch.org/>

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/eutr2013/index_en.htm

⁸ <https://www.earthsight.org.uk/>

registered in Belize and Panama in the name of his wife,” says Tara Ganesh from Earthsight (Earthsight, 2018a). “The head of the forestry authority is accused of having pocketed bribes from four timber companies to the tune of 13.6 million Euros between 2011 and 2014” (Earthsight, 2018a). The Earthsight (2018a) reported that “ghost trains” having false papers and full loads of logs find their way across the border with Romania at night. A forestry director was caught red-handed offering police officers \$10,000 “tribute money” to turn a blind eye to illegal logging activities. Since only Ukrainian firewood and sawn wood can be exported, exports of such woods are on rise. There is a trick in this too. Higher quality timber is deliberately declared a lower grade wood, purely falsely. The greedy criminal system behind such nexus is so strong that it engages into corruption various actors at all levels – from lawyers to bankers, and from forestry directors to customs and state railway officials. The WWF inspected 149 sites over 18 months and estimated that as much as 1.4 million cubic metres of timber is being illegally felled in the Ukrainian Carpathians alone each year, compared with 4 million cubic metres of official harvesting (Earthsight, 2018b, 2018c). Anonymous sources in the government reiterated, “The forest control system in Ukraine is not functioning properly. There are fundamental problems with how felling licences are being issued in Ukraine, in particular as regards approvals for sanitary felling. It should be unthinkable that an enterprise is in charge of issuing a felling licence for its own operations, which is currently the case for all sanitary felling” (Earthsight, 2018a). The EU is by far the largest destination for Ukrainian wood exports, representing 70 per cent of the total. EU purchases have been rising rapidly, breaking 1 billion Euro in 2017. Earthsight estimates that at least 40 per cent of this wood was harvested or traded illegally (Earthsight, 2018a).

Conclusion

What is overall learning from the analytical account of this interrelationship of the greed, globalization and environmental catastrophe? The greed of acquiring resources, money, materials and power is very common and not restricted to one or two persons. Sometimes, the whole society is psychologically sick. Everyone wants to gain one benefit or the other in a chain of nexus. Yet, the champions of greedy society are undoubtedly the top capitalists operating the global institutions and controlling the chains of globalization down the line. Hence, the implications of greed are not only economic, but also social, psychological and, ultimately, environmental. So-called civilized world has damaged the planet most; this is witnessed when comparison is done with already existing examples of infringed and threatened Indigenous societies. There can be series of theoretical recommendations to address the greed syndrome by a human at psychological level. However, it might be futile exercise, as the human learns from his/her mistakes and its grave implications.

References

- American Psychiatric Association (Ed.) (2000). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-IV-TR®*. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Publishing, Inc.
- Angres, D.H. and Bettinardi-Angres, K. (2008). The disease of addiction: Origins, treatment, and recovery. *Disease-a-Month*, 54(10): 696-721. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.disamonth.2008.07.002>
- Arnett, J.J. (2002). The Psychology of Globalization. *American Psychologist*, 57(10): 774–783. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037//0003-066X.57.10.774>.
- Barnett, M.N. and Duvall, R. (Eds.) (2005). *Power in global governance* (Vol. 98). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Baslar, K. (2011). *The Concept of the Common Heritage of Mankind in International Law*. The Netherlands: Kluwer Law.
- Bernard, H. and Gerlach, S. (1998). Does the Term Structure Predict Recessions?: the International Evidence (No. 1892). Centre for Economic Policy Research, London, UK.
- Black, D.W. (2007). Antisocial Personality Disorder. Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology, 4th edition. London: Wiley, 19 January 2010.
- Blas, J. and England, A. (2008). Arable land, the new gold rush, African and poor countries cautioned. *Afrik News*, 20 August 2008.

- Boydell, S. (2001). Philosophical Perception of Pacific Property: Land as a Communal Asset in Fiji. Pacific Rim Real Estate Society, January 2004, p.21.
- Brewer, J.A. and Potenza, M.N. (2008). The neurobiology and genetics of impulse control disorders: relationships to drug addictions. *Biochemical Pharmacology*, 75(1): 63-75. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016%2Fj.bcp.2007.06.043>
- Camarena, B., Rinetti, G., Cruz, C., Hernández, S., de la Fuente, J.R. and Nicolini, H. (2001). Association study of the serotonin transporter gene polymorphism in obsessive-compulsive disorder. *The International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology*, 4(03): 269-272. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1461145701002516>
- Change, I.C. (1996). The science of climate change. *Second Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Crews, F.T., Zou, J. and Qin, L. (2011). Induction of innate immune genes in brain create the neurobiology of addiction. *Brain, Behavior and Immunity*, 25: S4-S12. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2011.03.003>
- Cunney, F.C. and Hill, R.B. (1999). *Famine, Conflict, and Response: A Basic Guide* (pp. 117-126). West Hartford: Kumarian Press.
- D'Souza, J. (1995). Greed: Crises, Causes, and Solutions. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 5(7): 1-6.
- Davies, J. (2006). Capitalism as an environmental issue. Blog, available at: <http://www.gocatgo.com/texts/capenv.html>
- Denys, D., Zohar, J. and Westenberg, H.G. (2004). The role of dopamine in obsessive compulsive disorder: preclinical and clinical evidence. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 65: 11-17. Available online at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15554783/>
- Di Chiara, G. and Bassareo, V. (2007). Reward system and addiction: what dopamine does and doesn't do. *Current Opinion in Pharmacology*, 7(1): 69-76. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coph.2006.11.003>
- Earthsight (2018a). Complicit in Corruption: How billion-dollar firms and EU governments are failing Ukraine's forests. July 2018. Available online at: https://fe8a03e2-1131-44e7-a06a-fb468c2a30d4.filesusr.com/ugd/624187_673e3aa69ed84129bdf91b6aa9ec17.pdf
- Earthsight (2018b). Ukraine PM announces crackdown on illegal logging and timber corruption. News, 18 July 2018. Available online at: <https://www.earthsight.org.uk/news/investigation/ukraine-pm-crackdown-illegal-logging-timber-complicit-corruption>
- Earthsight (2018c). Fate of Ukraine's forests hangs in the balance, as new reports confirm the scale of illegal logging and timber corruption. News, 23 November 2018. Available online at: <https://www.earthsight.org.uk/news/press-release/complicit-corruption/ukraine-fate-forests-in-balance-new-report-confirms-scale-illegal-logging>
- Freud, S. (1914). On narcissism: An introduction. In: J. Strachey *et al.* (Trans.), *The Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud, Volume XIV*. London: Hogarth Press.
- Fromm, E. (1939). Selfishness and self-love. *Psychiatry*, 2(4): 507-523.
- Furnham, A., Richards, S.C. and Paulhus, D.L. (2013). The dark triad of personality: A 10 year review. *Social And Personality Psychology Compass*, 7: 199-216. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12018>.
- Girault, J.A. and Greengard, P. (2004). The neurobiology of dopamine signaling. *Archives of Neurology*, 61(5): 641-644. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1001/archneur.61.5.641>
- Golomb, E. (1995). *Trapped in The Mirror*. New York: Harper Collins.
- Groopman, L.C. and Cooper, A.M. (1995). *Narcissistic personality disorder*. Washington, DC: Gabbard GO. & American Psychiatric Press, Inc., pp.2327-2343.
- Hansen, J., Sato, M., Ruedy, R., Lacis, A. and Oinas, V. (2000). Global warming in the twenty first century: An alternative scenario. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 97(18): 9875-9880.
- Held, D. (1998). Democratization and globalization. In: D. Archibugi, D. Held and M. Kohler (Eds.), *Re-imagining political community* (pp.11-27). Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Holbrook, M.B. (1987). Mirror, mirror, on the wall, what's unfair in the reflections on advertising? *Journal of Marketing*, 51(3).

- Ilić, I. and Hafner, P. (2015). Environmental Aspects of the Process of Globalization – Negative Implications and Crisis. *Facta Universitatis Series: Economics and Organization*, 12(2): 109-120. Available online at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/228550099.pdf>
- Kauer, J.A. and Malenka, R.C. (2007). Synaptic plasticity and addiction. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 8(11): 844-858. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2234>
- Klein, N. (2011). Capitalism vs. the Climate. *The Nation*, 9 November 2011. Available online at: <https://www.thenation.com/article/archive/capitalism-vs-climate/>
- Koković, D. (2010). Ecology as a way of life. Svarog, Independent University of Banja Luka, No.:1
- Lasch, C. (1991). *The culture of narcissism: American life in an age of diminishing expectations*. New York: WW Norton & Company.
- Lehermayr, C., Reinhart, S. and Kaiser, J. (2020). Timber mafia and deforestation in Romania. *Blog*, 6 April 2020. Osservatorio Balcani e Caucaso Transeuropa, Trento (TN), Italy. Available online at: <https://www.balcanicaucaso.org/eng/Areas/Romania/Timber-mafia-and-deforestation-in-Romania-200194>
- Lomborg, B. (2009). *Global crises, global solutions*. New York, USA: Cambridge University Press.
- Malešević K. (2004). *Man against himself - visits from social ecology*. Belgrade: Samizdat 92.
- Meehl, G.A., Zwiers, F., Evans, J., Knutson, T., Mearns, L. and Whetton, P. (2000). Trends in extreme weather and climate events: Issues related to modeling extremes in projections of future climate change. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 81(3): 427-436. Available online at: https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/bams/81/3/1520-0477_2000_081_0427_tiewac_2_3_co_2.xml
- Moshagen, M., Hilbig, B.E. and Zettler, I. (2018). The dark core of personality. *Psychological Review*, 125: 656–688. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000111>.
- Mussel, P. and Hewig, J. (2016). The life and times of individuals scoring high and low on dispositional greed. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 64: 52–60. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2016.07.002>.
- Newell, P. and Paterson, M. (2010). *Climate capitalism: global warming and the transformation of the global economy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Nikelly, A. (2006). The pathogenesis of greed: Causes and consequences. *International Journal of Applied Psychoanalytic Studies*, 3(1): 65-78. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/aps.50>.
- Olivier, J.G., Peters, J.A. and Janssens-Maenhout, G. (2012). Trends in global CO₂ emissions 2012 report. PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency.
- Postel, S. (1997). *Last oasis: facing water scarcity*. New York: WW Norton & Company.
- Radić Jovanović, D., Ignjatović, M., Vljaković, M. and Đarmati, D., (2012). The impact of transport on the environment and human health. Sanitary Ecology Society, Belgrade.
- Ravuva, A. (1983). *Vaka I Taukei: The Fijian Way of Life*. Java: Institute of Pacific Studies, University of South Pacific, p.7.
- Robertson, A.F. (2013). *Greed: Gut feelings, growth, and history*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
- Salamone, J.D. (1992). Complex motor and sensorimotor functions of striatal and accumbens dopamine: involvement in instrumental behavior processes. *Psychopharmacology*, 107(2-3): 160-174.
- Schultz, D. and Schultz, S. (2004). *Theories of personality*. Noida, India: Cengage Learning.
- Schulze, L., Dziobek, I., Vater, A., Heekeren, H.R., Bajbouj, M., Renneberg, B., Heuser, I. and Roepke, S. (2013). Gray matter abnormalities in patients with narcissistic personality disorder. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 47(10): 1363-1369. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2013.05.017>
- Silberbauer, G.B. (1994). A Sense of Place. In: Burch, E.S. and Ellanna, L.J. (Eds.), *Key Issues in Hunter-Gatherer Research*, Oxford: Berg, p. 131.
- Siriner, I. and Nenička, L. (2011). Globalisation: Dimensions and Impacts. *International Journal of Politics and Economics* - IJOPEC, London.
- Sjöberg, R.L., Ducci, F., Barr, C.S., Newman, T.K., Dell'Osso, L., Virkkunen, M. and Goldman, D. (2007). A nonadditive interaction of a functional MAO-A VNTR and testosterone predicts antisocial behavior. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 33(2): 425-430. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1038%2Fsj.npp.1301417>

- Smrečnik, T. (2002), Social Ecology - basic themes and theoretical perspective. Faculty of Security Studies, Belgrade.
- Steg, L. and Vlek, C. (2009). Encouraging pro-environmental behavior: An integrative review and research agenda. *J. Environ. Psychol.*, 29: 309–317. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2008.10.004>
- Stern, P. (2000). Toward a coherent theory of environmentally significant behavior. *J. Soc. Issues*, 56: 407–424. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111%2F0022-4537.00175> also available online at: https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/document/download/2170a4cf4ce55cbdfb2856011a8930bb.pdf/08_stern_2000.pdf
- Taylor, S. (2014). Ecocide: The Psychology of Environmental Destruction: Why Can't We Live in Harmony with the Rest of Nature? *Psychology Today*, June 18, 2014. Available online at: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/out-the-darkness/201406/ecocide-the-psychology-environmental-destruction>
- The Battle in Seattle (1999). *The Economist*, 353(8147): 21–23.
- United Nations (2006). Water: a shared responsibility (Vol. 2). UN-HABITAT, Nairobi.
- Webster, M. (2013). *Merriam-Webster online dictionary*. Connecticut, USA: Webster
- Zetland, D. (2011). *The end of abundance: economic solutions to water scarcity*. Navi Mumbai, India: Aguanomics Press.

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